

MARKETING STRATEGY FOR ENTERING THE CONFECTIONERY INDUSTRY MARKET

¹Atakuziev S.A., ²Boriskina T.B.

^{1,2}Volgograd State Technical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10363566>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the features of external economic activity of the confectionery industry. It examines the main theoretical aspects of international marketing, and also provides the results of an analysis of the experience of the largest, most successful companies in the confectionery industry.*

Keywords: *international marketing, foreign economic activity, strategy for entering the international market, export, direct investment.*

The relevance of research. Nowadays, the trend of market globalization is becoming one of the determining factors for the activities of many companies. The competitiveness of an enterprise is now determined not only by its marketing policy within its own state, but also by its behavior in the international arena.

For enterprises in the confectionery industry, this problem becomes especially relevant, since due to the specifics of the market and consumer preferences in different cultures, companies cannot always count on success using standardized strategies and methods. Based on this, we posed a research question, which we will answer within the framework of the article: What should be the marketing strategy of a confectionery enterprise when entering the international market so that the attempt to enter is crowned with success?

At the same time, by a successful attempt to enter the international market we do not mean a one-time shipment, but regular work in a specific foreign market, which implies receiving profit from the company's work in this direction as a result. As a research hypothesis, we highlight the assumption that foreign economic activity, organized in the form of export marketing with an adopted strategy of innovation in the confectionery market, ensures a faster and more sustainable conquest of international market share.

Ignorance of the peculiarities of foreign markets, laws, rules adopted there, characteristics of consumer behavior and many other details becomes the main problem of enterprises wishing to expand their zone of influence. Even the company's products, which are in great demand in the domestic market, cannot be guaranteed to be successful in the international market; for each country, demand will have individual characteristics. In such cases, companies resort to international marketing to reduce uncertainty.

First of all, it is worth noting that when trying to enter a foreign market, the company moves to a fundamentally new type of activity - foreign economic activity. In some cases, it may be fundamentally different from the company's usual activities in the domestic market and require more resources and development costs. Foreign economic activity is a combination of production, economic, organizational, economic and commercial functions of firms.

International marketing is a system of planning, implementation, control and analysis of activities to influence the market environment and adapt to its conditions in a company that operates in more than one country. Marketing goals in international business are determined by the expediency of entering the market of a specific country, determining the characteristics (type,

price, etc.) of the product being promoted, the features of the marketing program for entry, the desired results, and the possibilities of developing an adaptable strategy for entering the international market. All decisions must be made based on a detailed analysis of the environment and possible risks that the company may face in the new country.

The simplest and most common strategy for entering the international market is exporting. Export requires minimal capital investment; a global goal regarding the sales market is not always set. Products are manufactured on-site and are not always upgraded for the export market. Indirect export is carried out through work with international intermediaries. The investment in this case is minimal. The risks associated with such an organization of activities are small.

Another option for organizing exports is direct export. In this case, the company creates special divisions engaged exclusively in foreign economic activities and changes its organizational structure. In this case, the company's risks become higher, but this allows you to slightly reduce product prices by reducing costs and increase your potential income. Next, the company can follow two paths - working with distribution companies in foreign territories or organizing its own branch in the territory of the potential sales market. The branch expands the company's capabilities by organizing local sales in the manner necessary for the company, allowing it to quickly respond to market challenges. Distributing companies can perform the same functions for the company, however, for certain payments and commissions.

The last and most interesting strategy for entering the international market is the direct investment strategy. It involves the creation of assembly or manufacturing branch enterprises on the foreign market. By organizing production, it is possible in the long term to reduce costs and production costs due to cheaper labor and lower transport and other variable costs.

By implementing such a strategy, the company retains full control over the enterprise and its investments, and can develop its production and marketing strategies as it sees fit, achieving its long-term international goals. The global confectionery market is characterized by the presence of three main segments according to product classification: sugar products (22%), chocolate products (35%) and flour products (43%).

The main international confectionery companies are: Mars Inc., Nestle SA, Ferrero Group, Kraft Foods Co., Hershey Company, etc. In Russia, the United Confectioners confectionery holding, which includes 19 confectionery enterprises throughout Russia, is actively working with foreign partners. incl. such giants as "Red October", "RotFront" and "Babaevsky" and others, as well as the holding LLC "KDV-Group". Thus, another way for a confectionery enterprise to gain market share is to develop a unique product with a unique recipe that the consumer will "fall in love" with. Based on the results of the work, we can conclude that the hypothesis stated in the article is partially confirmed. The innovation strategy is indeed one of the most effective, however, not only the export strategy, but also direct investment can be called successful. This strategy allows you to see the foreign market from the inside, quickly responding to its needs.

REFERENCES

1. Алексунин В. А. [и др.]. Маркетинг в отраслях и сферах деятельности: учебник / В. А. Алексунин и др. // – М.: «Дашков и к», 2009. – С. 360.
2. Гусева М. В. Маркетинговые стратегии международных диверсифицированных компаний в условиях глобализации мировой экономики / М. В. Гусева // Аспирант. – Ростов-на-Дону: Южный университет (ИУБиП), 2015.-С. 100 – 102.

3. Котлер Ф., Армстронг Г. Основы маркетинга. Профессиональное издание: пер. с английского. – М.: ООО «И. Д. Вильямс», 2009. – с. 1072.
4. Кузьменко С. С. Специфика деятельности международных кондитерских компаний / С. С. Кузьменко // Азимут научных исследований: экономика и управление. – Тольятти: Некоммерческое Партнерство "Институт направленного образования", 2014. – С. 63-65.
5. Моргунов В.И., Моргунов С.В. Международный маркетинг/учеб. пособие / В. И. Моргунов и др.// – М.: «Дашков и К», 2014.
6. Мун С. Сегментирование рынка и разработка стратегии выхода на международный рынок на основе стиля жизни / С. Мун // Вестник УрФУ. Серия Экономика и управление. – Екатеринбург: Уральский федеральный университет имени первого Президента России Б.Н. Ельцина (Екатеринбург), 2009. – С. 66-74.
7. Попова Е. А. Методика разработки международной стратегии развития компании. / Е. А. Попова // Модели, системы, сети в экономике, технике, природе и обществе. – Пенза: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью "Центр анализа и развития кластерных систем", 2015. – С. 72-80.
8. Соловьев Б. А. Маркетинг: учебное пособие / Б. А. Соловьева//. – М.: Инфра – м, 2009. – С. 383.
9. Соловьева Д. В., Чернышева Е. К. Комплексный метод маркетингового анализа зарубежных рынков с целью разработки стратегии международного развития компании. Монография / Д. В. Соловьева, Е. К. Чернышева //
10. «Маркетинговые стратегии компаний на рынках развитых и развивающихся стран». – М.: Российский университет дружбы народов (РУДН), 2013. – С. 75– 86.
11. Шишлова С.Е. Развитие внешнеэкономической деятельности российских предприятий / С. Е. Шишлова // Известия тульского государственного университета. Экономические и юридические науки. - Тула.: Тульский государственный университет, 2013. – С. 276 – 279.